

Using Regional Products to Study Regional Representation in the European Parliament

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Policy Recommendations

1. We analyze written questions in the European Parliament to investigate regional representation.
2. We focus on Geographical Indications such as Feta or Champagne: these protected regional products provide clear incentives and a reliable measurement of regional representation.
3. We find that Members of European Parliament often mention products from their birth region. Their questions focus on contentious products and politicized free trade agreements.
4. Our data shows more regional representation by MEPs from countries with regional lists for EP elections.
5. We conclude with the implications of our research for representation in the European Union: regional lists lead to more regional representation, so transnational lists may lead to more transnational representation.

1. Introduction

This Policy Brief and the underlying article (see Further Information) uses parliamentary questions (PQs) in the European Parliament to study territorial representation in the EU. It codes and analyses the 428 written questions on Geographical Indications posed by Members of European Parliament (MEPs) during the period 2009-2019. Geographical Indications (GIs) such as Roquefort cheese or Bourgogne wine are an ideal policy area to study the political economy of territorial representation. Their defined production regions provide both clear incentives and a

reliable measurement of territorial representation.

The study of parliamentary questions (PQs) in the EP has received increasing attention in recent years, either to study oversight dynamics (Proksch & Slapin, 2011; Sorace, 2018), politicization of issues and competition over issue ownership (Meijers & van der Veer, 2019) or territorial representation (Brack & Costa, 2019; Chiru, 2022; Sozzi, 2016). It is to this latter perspective of territorial representation that our study contributes in particular. Because of their link to a specific territory, GIs as a policy area are uniquely

suitable to determine whether national or regional representation is at work.

Understanding the incentives and behavior of MEPs is important: the EP is a key actor in EU decision making and is seen as important for democratic legitimacy. While MEPs are often expected to keep a European perspective, individual MEPs also face incentives for the representation of more narrow national or regional economic interests. In addition to the importance of understanding MEPs' incentives and behavior, parliamentary questions on GIs offer insight into the substantive concern of MEPs qua GIs.

Our contributions are threefold. First, we construct a dataset of all EP questions on GIs over the period 2009-2019 (N=428), classified by MEP, theme, and GI products mentioned. Themes and subthemes were coded by hand. In terms of territorial representation, we code regional representation if an MEP asks a question on a GI from their birth region. Second, we qualitatively analyze the content of the questions. Third, we identify the effect of regional lists in EP elections on regional representation.

Our findings point to three overarching take-aways. First, a lot of questions on GIs concern international trade, and especially politicized trade agreements and products. Second, there is a lot of regional representation in GI questions: 25% of questions relate to a GI from the MEP's birth region, and an additional 34% to a GI from their country. Especially MEPs with a nationalist or regionalist party ideology are involved in these. Third, MEPs from countries with regional lists for EP elections are more likely to engage in regional representation.

2. Data and Methods

The aim of this study is to gain insights in the drivers of written parliamentary questions about GIs, as well as on the extent of territorial representation involved. That requires data on parliamentary questions and on MEPs over the period studied. Given the increased role for the EP since the 2009 Treaty of Lisbon, we focus on the two most recently completed legislatures: EP7 (2009-2014) and EP8 (2014-2019).

The main explanatory analyses will be conducted on a database of all MEPs serving in EP7 and EP8 (2009-2014; 2014-2019). For each MEP, we counted the number of Parliamentary Questions (PQs) on GIs per calendar year, as well as the number of PQs with regional representation. We collected data on MEPs from the EP website and other public sources where needed.

The unit of analysis is the MEP, per calendar year (separate for the two halves of 2014 in each of the legislatures). MEPs who served in both legislatures hence appear 12 times in the dataset.

Our main dependent variable is *Regional Representation*, which we code as 1 when an MEP's question refers to a GI from their birth region, such as when an MEP from Normandy asks a parliamentary question about *Camembert de Normandie*.

We have explanatory variables at several levels: individual (MEP), political party, and country. Examples include whether an MEP served on the EP committee on Agriculture and Rural Development (AGRI), an MEP's ideology, and the number of GIs in the MEP's country. Our main explanatory variable of interest is *Regional lists*, which is 1 for countries that elect MEPs with subnational

lists through constituencies or districts: Belgium, Italy, and the United Kingdom. France, Ireland, and Poland also use regional lists, but there is a mismatch between the electoral regions and the NUTS₁ regions used to code regional representation. Hence, we do not use data for France, Ireland, and Poland in the regressions of regional representation.

3. Results

With respect to the content of the questions, the biggest theme is ‘External trade’ (159 questions), covering four subthemes. First, questions where the EU has an offensive interest (59 questions), i.e. seeking protection of EU GIs outside of the EU Single Market. Second, questions where the EU has a defensive interest (47 questions), such as concerns that opening up trade will lead to competition with cheap non-GI imports. Third, questions on whether specific GIs would be put on the lists for protection in specific free trade agreements (FTAs) such as TTIP with the US or CETA with Canada (47 questions). Fourth, questions on trade and trade agreements among third countries outside of the EU (6 questions).

We coded the specific Free Trade Agreements (FTAs) mentioned in ‘external trade’ questions and find that seven trade agreements or countries were mentioned more than 5 times: TTIP (50 questions), CETA (23 times), China (15 times), Morocco (11 times), Mercosur (14 times), the WTO (10 times) and the United Kingdom/Brexit (7 times). TTIP and CETA, arguably the two most politicized EU trade agreements that were under negotiation over the time period 2009-2019 (De Bièvre & Poletti, 2020), are clear outliers.

The other main themes are Regulation, Applications, and Compliance. ‘Regulation’

(114 questions) concerns general inquiries into the evolution and (potential) adaptation of the GI legislative framework (e.g. asking whether non-food products could also become eligible for GI protection) and GIs in relation to other pieces of EU or domestic regulation, such as country-of-origin labelling (COOL). ‘Application’ questions (74 questions) on the other hand specifically mention certain GI products, to ask about the status of a GI approval request, or whether the Commission would consider supporting a GI request for a specific product. The theme ‘Compliance’ (71 questions) is the internal counterpart of ‘External trade’ as questions here concern possible imitation or evocation of GIs (and associated inspection requests) within the EU single market.

Concerning the type of GIs that are mentioned, the results especially point to the political salience of GIs of cheese. This is in contrast to the relatively few questions on wine, whereas these are in general the product category that has the most protected products.

The results in terms of territorial representation are in line with expectations that the policy area of GIs is an outlier. In total, we find that approximately 60% of questions (254/428) involve some form of either regional or national representation, with the former accounting for 25% of questions. The earliest study by Raunio (1996) and the large-N analysis by Brack & Costa (2019) found an upper limit of 33% of (sub)national representation. It is clear therefore that GIs is definitely a topic dominated by territorial considerations, where MEPs are (or like to be seen as) concerned about products stemming from their region or country.

In terms of the drivers of regional representation, we focus on a country characteristic that is hypothesized to give

more incentives for regional representation: the use of regional lists. So far, the literature has suffered from the fact that there may be other sources of variation at the country level that are hard to control for. If regional lists correlate with such unobserved country characteristics, the findings so far may be spurious. In contrast, our focus on PQs on GIs only has the important advantage that we can control for the key driver of PQs at the country level, namely whether a country has many GIs. Controlling for that and a range of other variables, we indeed find that MEPs from countries that use regional lists for MEP elections engage more in regional representation, as Figure 1 shows. It shows the predicted probability of an MEP asking at least one question about a GI from their region, on an annual basis. When regional lists are used for EP elections, the probability of regional representation more than doubles. This finding is robust to excluding Italy from the regression, so our effect is not driven by Italy.

4. Policy Implications

Members of the European Parliament are often assumed to represent the European citizens. However, they also face incentives for the representation of more narrow regional economic interests. We argue in the paper underlying this policy brief (see Further Information) that Parliamentary Questions on Geographical Indications provide a unique window to study the incentives and behaviour of MEPs, especially with regards to regional representation.

Descriptively, we find that there is a lot of regional representation in GI questions. Where others found less than one third of questions had a (sub)national focus (Raunio, 1996; Brack and Costa, 2019), we found 25% of questions had a focus on the MEP's birth

region, and an additional 34% on the MEP's country – so in total almost 60% of (sub)national representation. This shows that even transnational parliaments are used for (sub)national representation, especially on topics with a direct regional link, such as GIs.

A lot of questions on GIs concern international trade, and especially politicized trade agreements and products. TTIP and CETA, arguably the two most politicized EU trade agreements that were under negotiation over the time period 2009-2019, are clear outliers.

Looking at the drivers of regional representation, we find that it is more likely for MEPs from countries with regional lists for EP elections. Focusing on GIs has two key advantages. It allows for a straightforward coding of regional representation: MEPs asking questions on GIs from the region of their birth. Second, one can control for the most important cross-national determinant of the overall number of questions, namely the number of GIs a country has. Nevertheless, because this finding is identified cross-nationally from a small number of countries using regional lists, caution remains necessary in interpreting it.

Our findings are relevant for debates on the democratic deficit in the EU, and the role of the European Parliament in remediating that deficit. On the one hand, regional representation indicates that MEPs are close to their citizens. For those advocating a European 'democracy' (Cheneval & Schimmelfennig, 2013) or a Europe of regions, this may be highly desirable. On the other hand, if one believes MEPs should represent the European people as a whole, these findings are problematic. Depending on the stance one takes, using regional lists for European Parliament elections should either be encouraged or discouraged (Hix &

Hagemann, 2009). In fact, believers in a European demos may consider our findings an additional argument for transnational lists rather than national, let alone regional lists. Extrapolating from our findings, transnational lists can be expected to generate more transnational representation.

To conclude, Geographical Indications such as Scotch Whisky, Liszki sausage, and Prosecco receive political attention in the European Parliament. As could have been expected, GIs are an outlier case in terms of territorial representation, as 25% of written parliamentary questions on GIs focus on GI products from the MEP's birth region. MEPs from countries with regional lists for EP elections are especially likely to engage in regional representation, which is relevant for the debate on the democratic nature of the European Parliament.

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

References

- Brack, N., & Costa, O. (2019). Parliamentary Questions and Representation of Territorial Interests in the EP. In O. Costa (Ed.), *The European Parliament in Times of EU Crisis: Dynamics and Transformations* (pp. 225–254). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-97391-3_11
- Cheneval, F., & Schimmelfennig, F. (2013). The Case for Democracy in the European Union. *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies*, 51(2), 334–350. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-5965.2012.02262.x>
- Chiru, M. (2022). Electoral incentives for territorial representation in the European Parliament. *Journal of European Integration*, 44(2), 277–298. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07036337.2021.1890067>
- De Bièvre, D., & Poletti, A. (2020). Towards Explaining Varying Degrees of Politicization of EU Trade Agreement Negotiations. *Politics and Governance*, 8(1), 243–253. <https://doi.org/10.17645/pag.v8i1.2686>
- Hix, S., & Hagemann, S. (2009). Could changing the electoral rules fix European parliament elections ? *Politique européenne*, 28(2), 37–52. <https://doi.org/10.3917/poeu.028.0037>
- Meijers, M. J., & van der Veer, H. (2019). Issue Competition without Electoral Incentives? A Study of Issue Emphasis in the European Parliament. *The Journal of Politics*, 81(4), 1240–1253. <https://doi.org/10.1086/704224>
- Proksch, S.-O., & Slapin, J. B. (2011). Parliamentary questions and oversight in the European Union. *European Journal of Political Research*, 50(1), 53–79. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-6765.2010.01919.x>
- Raunio, T. (1996). Parliamentary questions in the European parliament: Representation, information and control. *The Journal of Legislative Studies*, 2(4), 356–382. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13572339608420492>
- Sorace, M. (2018). Legislative Participation in the EU: An analysis of questions, speeches,

motions and declarations in the 7th European Parliament. *European Union Politics*, 19(2), 299-320. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1465116518757701>

Sozzi, F. (2016). Electoral foundations of parliamentary questions: Evidence from the European Parliament. *The Journal of Legislative Studies*, 22(3), 349-367. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13572334.2016.1202650>

Further Information:

Huysmans, M., & Gheyle, N. (2023). [Regional representation in the European Parliament: Parliamentary Questions on Geographical Indications](#). *USE Working Paper Series*, 23(9), 1-40.

Figure 1. Predicted probability of Regional Representation based on a statistical logit model with controls.

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